

LEXICAL FEATURES OF ANTHROPHONYMS

Sharipova Malokhat

Tashkent Institute of Textile Light Industry
<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890365>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26th April 2023

Accepted: 02nd May 2023

Online: 03rd May 2023

KEY WORDS

Anthrponyms, cognitive-discursive, anthroponymic dictionaries, transcription, linguistic situation, anthophonemic formula, anthroponymic lexicography.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the use of English anthroponyms in the social sphere, anthroponymic formulas, signals of anthroponyms. It also discusses some of the research that has emerged as a result of a comparative analysis of the etymology of anthroponyms with Russian and other languages. The nominative value of names, anthroponymic formulas, and signals of anthroponyms are also discussed.

Currently, it is generally accepted that the scientific paradigm has changed in linguistics: the transition from linguistics “internal”, systemic and structural, to cognitive-discursive linguistics. According to E.S. Kubryakova, in recent decades “it has been realized that data on language can be used to illuminate a wider range of problems concerning both the nature of the human mind and intellect and its behavior, which is manifested in all processes of human interaction with the outside world and other people”. Modern researchers emphasize that the onomastic subsystems of the language are part of the linguistic pictures of the world: “The description of the onomastic picture of the world, based on the study of the principles of naming, the creation of a dictionary of onomastic vocabulary and the establishment of a list of realities that have been honored with the name, will, to a certain extent, allow us to approach the creation of a common inventory of connotative symbolic systems that determine different directions of the human spirit.

English anthroponymic lexicography, namely English anthroponymic dictionaries, which include exclusively personal names, is a poorly studied area that requires detailed consideration. The functional and structural characteristics of English-language anthroponymic dictionaries, as well as the ways of representing the semantic features of personal names in dictionaries, have not been sufficiently studied. The need to address these issues of describing English-language dictionaries determines the relevance of this study. In modern linguistics, the question of the structural and semantic structure of the English anthroponymic dictionary remains open and unexplored. Despite the popularity and diversity of modern English anthroponymic dictionaries, their status in the general lexicographic paradigm and their inherent structural and content features remain practically unexplored. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the structural-semantic and linguocultural analysis of

English-language anthroponymic dictionaries and the development of their typology. The object of the research is English anthroponyms, namely the first personal names that serve for the main identification of a person and are used in Great Britain and the USA. The subject of the research is the ways of representing English anthroponyms in the English anthroponymic dictionaries of the British, American and Russian editions. The whole research is to determine the peculiarities of the representation of English anthroponyms in special anthroponymic dictionaries. This goal assumes the solution of the following tasks:

1. to clarify the formal and substantive properties of English anthroponyms;
2. to establish the place of the anthroponymic dictionary in modern English-language lexicography;
3. to determine the composition and organization of the structure of the English anthroponymic dictionary;
4. to establish ways of representing the semantics of English personal names in the anthroponymic dictionary.

Undoubtedly, as the linguists A.B. Suslov and A.B. Superanskaya, “the role of a personal name in a person's life is very great. Each person can only be called by name, therefore all his good and all his bad deeds are made public thanks to his name”. Therefore, some names are dearly loved by the people and are used very often, while others, on the contrary, cause complete disgust and negative emotions associated with its bearer. Being an integral part of the life of any person, personal names, as part of the language system, have attracted the attention of researchers for a long time. As a result of this interest, a special section of onomastics has developed - anthroponymics, which studies the names of people (personal name, surname, patronymic, nickname, pseudonym). By the term “onomastics” we mean “a branch of linguistics that studies any proper names”. Anthroponymy studies anthroponyms; translated from Greek *anthropos* - “person” and *onyma* - “name”. The concept of “anthroponym” in modern linguistics is understood as any proper name that a person (or a group of people) can have, including a personal name, patronymic, surname, nickname, pseudonym, Cryptonym, nickname. Thus, an anthroponym is a broad concept that implies any way of naming a person in a formal and informal setting. The choice of this or that type of anthroponym depends on a number of different circumstances: national and cultural traditions of the people, age, place of residence, erudition, aesthetic education, social circle and just common sense. Another feature of this onomastic category is that each type of anthroponym is used only in a certain linguistic situation. In addition, different anthroponymic models are used in different countries. There are models of the same name (only a personal name is used for naming), two-name (personal name + last name, first name + nickname, etc.), three-name (personal name + middle name + last name, personal name + patronymic + last name, etc.) or multi-name models (personal name + several middle names + last name, etc.). Such naming models have evolved over a long period of time and are based on the cultural, historical and linguistic characteristics of a particular country. Further in our work, the anthroponym is considered as the first personal name serving for the main identification of a person. One of the difficulties traditionally faced by a translator when working on a text is the transmission of the so-called. non-equivalent linguistic units, those to which there is no correspondence in the target language. Such units are present at any level of

the language - phonetic, morphological, syntactic, lexical and phraseological. This article will describe the methods of transferring in Russian the most, perhaps, non-equivalent type of linguistic units - English proper names. On the one hand, one cannot speak of translating proper names in the full sense of the word. On the other hand, translation errors in the transfer of this layer of vocabulary are especially striking to the reader, and therefore it seems necessary to clearly describe the ways of "translation" of these language units. First of all, it should be noted that there are two main ways of transferring English proper names in Russian, namely, transcription and transliteration. The first is the transmission of the sound form of the word, the second is the transmission of its letter structure. In the old days, English (as well as others) proper names were mainly transliterated during translation. In essays on the history and culture of England, written in the 16-18 centuries, one can find such comical English surnames and place names for the modern reader as Newton, Stewing, Hawkesbury, etc. Nowadays, the undoubted priority in the transmission of proper names is recognized for transcription: it is believed that sound should be transmitted, not the literal form of the name. There are many exceptions to this general rule, since in the Russian language there are fixed forms of transferring some names, but they will be discussed later. First, we will consider the phonetic capabilities of the Russian language in the transmission of English sounds. Although the majority of Russian and English sounds are clearly comparable, it is obvious that our phonetic systems have some perceptible differences, and below will be described options for the transmission of non-equivalent phonemes, that is, those that do not have a direct correspondence in Russian. The sound [θ] in words like Heath, Smith, Thatcher, Thorn, Arthur, Cathy, Heathrow, etc. is usually conveyed by the sound [t]: Heath, Smith, Thatcher, Thorn, Arthur, Cathy, Heathrow. It is not recommended to transmit it by sound [s]. The sound [ð] in names like Rutherford, Warner Brothers, Heather, Feather is usually "translated" by the sound [z]: Rutherford, Warner Brothers, Heather, Feather, although for the sake of euphony the name Heather can be rendered as Heather. When passing diphthongs [ɛə] and [iə] in words like Blair, Shakespeare, Yorkshire, Delaware the unstressed diphthong element is ignored: Blair, Shakespeare, Yorkshire, Delaware. The transmission of the following English sounds, which have no equivalents in Russian, can be carried out in different ways. In some cases, traditions and requirements of modernity clash here, in others - the sound and graphic forms of the word. Consider the variants of the "translation" of the sound [w] in the following proper names: Winston, William, Winchester, Warwick, Watson, Washington, Warner, Wendy, Wood, Worcester. Traditionally, it was customary to convey this sound using Russian [v], and in the modern language there are firmly established forms with such a sound: only Dr. Watson, Winchester, Washington, etc. sound naturally in Russian. At the same time, in accordance with the requirements of modernity, this sound is transmitted using Russian [y]: Winston Churchill, Warner Brothers, Walter Trout, etc. The only exceptions are cases when the sound [w] in the original is followed by [u:], as in Wood, Worcester. Then the only possible option is to use the sound [in]: Wood, Worcester. We are dealing with the clash of traditions and requirements of today. (Note that the name of the county and city of Warwick was previously translated Warwick, that is, it was transliterated. Now it is transcribed - Warwick.) [8, p.113] What option should the translator choose if he comes across a proper name containing the sound [w]?

The general outlook and well-readiness of the translator will help him determine whether a given name in a given combination is an established, accepted form, whether this particular person or name is known to a literate native speaker of the Russian language, or is it a relatively new borrowing. In the first case, you should choose the traditional form - Dr. Watson, in the second - follow modern rules - Whitney Houston. The situation with the sound [h] is similar to that described above. In accordance with modern requirements, it is transmitted to the Russians [x]. For example, Heathrow, Hewlett, Heart, Hue, Hugo, etc. should sound like Heathrow, Hewlett, Hart, Hugh, Hugo. However, there are many well-established names and titles where this sound is transmitted using Russian [g]: Harry, Herbert, Hyde Park, Huckleberry, Hudson - Harry, Herbert, Hyde Park, Huckleberry, Hudson. It should be specially noted here that in the middle of the word the sound [h] is not pronounced, and therefore it is not "translated": Graham Green is the English writer Graham Green. The sound [ə:] also does not have an unambiguous equivalent in the Russian phonetic system, and it is transmitted, it must be admitted, as necessary. Sometimes the closest sound [yo] is used: basketball player Larry Bird is named Larry Bird, the name of the Hot Spurs team is transmitted as Hot Spurs. In other cases, apparently, the rules of Russian spelling (e is written instead of e) leave an imprint on the sound of the word. So the names Perth, Churchill, Bertha and others are "translated" as Perth, Churchill, Bertha. In the third cases, it is difficult to offer a logical explanation of the sound transmission method [ə:]. For example, the proper name Pearl is "translated" as Pearl, then as Pearl, then as Pearl (cf. Pearl Harbor). How can a translator choose the most appropriate option? If this is not an established word form (Churchill), it is recommended to focus on the requirement of the euphony of the word. The transliteration method remains applicable to some non-equivalent elements of the English graphic-phonetic system today. For example, the sound [r] is written even where it does not sound: Ford, Arthur, Baltimore, Moor, Darwin are "translated" as Ford, Arthur, Baltimore, More, Darwin. Neutral [ə] is conveyed by the Russian letter that corresponds to the English letter that forms this sound in the English word: Arthur, Eliot, Hampstead, Allan sound like Arthur, Eliot, Hampstead, Alan. Doubled consonants are usually doubled in translation, and by no means for adequate sound transmission, but in order to preserve the graphic form. Wed: Lloyd, Bennet, Bess, Willy, Rebecca - Lloyd, Bennet, Bess, Willie (or Willie), Rebecca. Note that the combination of letters ck can be interpreted as doubled [κ]: Becky - Becky. The above options for the transfer of non-equivalent English sounds will help the translator to choose the necessary graphical form of the name, surname or geographical name, which he may encounter when translating any text. In the most typical situation of translation of a modern text, of course, priority should be given to the transcriptions of proper names. However, it must be remembered that modern requirements for the "translation" of names and titles recede before the established decades, and sometimes centuries, traditional ways of writing some words. The transmission of a certain word in the "correct" way, from the point of view of modernity, may run counter to the norms fixed in the language. The receptor of the translation text will have natural difficulties in understanding such names and names as the state of Texas, or the city of Adelaide, or the poet Heinrich Heine, or the scientist Einstein, etc., although this is how these names are transcribed. For various reasons, norms for the transfer of certain proper names have been established in the Russian language, and the

translator, like any other user of the Russian language, must comply with these norms: the state of Texas, the city of Adelaide, the poet Heinrich Heine, the scientist Einstein, etc. Next, we will consider several groups English names that have a fixed form of transmission in Russian, and also discuss cases when the same name can be translated in two ways, depending on the context of its use. First of all, these names include the names of ancient Greek and ancient Roman mythological characters. Naturally, borrowing these names from Greek and Latin, the Russian language did not take into account the phonetic form that they have in English. Although the sound of the names Zeus, Hercules, Apollo, Venus, Orpheus, Jupiter, etc. is quite significantly different from the Russian Zeus, Hercules, Apollo, Venus, Orpheus, Jupiter, they are equivalents in the text, where it is about these mythological heroes. However, it should be noted that these names may well be called ordinary people - our contemporaries. In this case, as recommended above, they should be transcribed. For example, the American tennis player Venus Williams will be called Venus (not Venus) Williams in Russian. The second group of proper names, which can be translated in different ways in different contexts, are biblical names. And in this case, the phonetic form of the names of biblical characters in English is different than in Russian. But the Bible was translated into Russian in time immemorial and a modern translator, of course, must follow the established norms and "translate" Jesus, Moses, John, Judas, Eve, Cain, Abraham, Michael, Isaac, Joseph, etc. like Jesus, Moses, John, Judas, Eve, Cain, Abraham, Michael, Isaac, Joseph, etc. in those contexts where it is about these historical (or mythological?) Personalities. In the same place where ordinary mortals are called by biblical names, which happens extremely often, the translator must again follow the rule of transcribing his own names. Therefore, the actor's Russian name is Michael Cain, writers Isaac Asimov and Joseph Conrad, rock group Judas' Priest, singer and composer John Lennon, etc.

William, James, Henry, Elizabeth, Mary, etc. should be transcribed if they belong to representatives of the common people, and sound, respectively, like Charles, William, James, Henry (this is the norm), Elizabeth and Mary. However, when it comes to kings and queens, these names are "translated" differently. Compare: Charles XII, William the Conqueror, James I, Henry VIII, Elizabeth II, Mary Stuart, etc. When translating such proper names, one must take into account the context of their use. A competent translator should not indulge in statements such as "Threw lightning arrows", or "Moses led the people of Israel in the desert for forty years," or "King James was on the throne for two years." Let's make a few comments about the translation of English geographic names. With them, the situation is simpler, because in case of doubt, the translator can refer to the English-Russian regional geographic dictionary, where he will find the names of most countries, states, counties, regions, cities, etc. In general, the transfer of geographical names is carried out on based on the same priorities as the "translation" of people's names: preference is given to transcription. Wed: the city of Tucson "translates" as Tucson. However, we will give a few examples when there may be some doubts about the translation of a particular name. Underlying doubts in most cases are resolved with the help of a dictionary. Some compound names are subject to the so-called. partial translation. This primarily applies to names containing the elements New, United, Republic, Commonwealth, as well as the names of the cardinal points - North, South, East, West. Usually these elements are translated by the corresponding Russian equivalents: New Zealand, New Orleans, New South Wales, the United Kingdom, the French Republic, the

Commonwealth of Independent States, North Carolina, West Virginia, etc. However, in some other cases, the phonetic form of all the elements of the compound name is transmitted: New York, New Hampshire, East River (East River - a city in the USA), etc. Therefore, the translator should be careful about the transfer of such names. In geographical names, consisting exclusively of common words, all their constituent elements are usually translated. Wed: Cape of Good Hope - Cape of Good Hope, Lake Superior - Lake Superior, Pacific Ocean - Pacific Ocean, Rocky Mountains - Rocky Mountains, Ivory Coast - Ivory Coast, although on some maps you can find a transcription of the French name of this African country - Cat d'Ivoire... In this regard, we note that when transferring French proper names, the French sound of the word is also preserved. For example, Yves Saint Laurent is transcribed as Yves Saint Laurent, Jean Louis Mauger as Jean Louis Mauger, Jean Paul Belmondaux as Jean Paul Belmondo, etc. At the same time, German names are more often transliterated. Compare: the surnames Freud and Reuter sound, respectively, as [froid] and [roiter], but "translated" as Freud and Reuter. T. about. if proper names of non-English origin are encountered in the text, the translator must transmit them according to the rules for the transfer of French, German, etc. personal names.

In conclusion, we point out once again that choosing one of the two existing methods of transferring English proper names - transcription and transliteration - can be a difficult task, and to successfully solve it, the translator will need not only knowledge of phonetic correspondences, but also a broad outlook, well-read and a high level of general culture. In recent decades, an anthropological reorientation has become apparent in the sciences of the sign order, and primarily in linguistics, the object of which is increasingly becoming the "ego-oriented linguistic space". One of the most important modern trends in the study of "ego-centered linguistic space" is associated with the allocation of microsystems, units of which are united by some common feature of a formal and / or meaningful plan. These microsystems include the names of one person, a person - an anthropolexic microsystem, within which common nouns and proper names are distinguished. It is the latter, known in linguistics under the name of anthroponyms, that are discussed in detail in this work from the point of view of the possibilities of conveying the pragmatic (in a broad sense, when we mean the whole sum of connotations - social, cultural, ethical, historical, emotive, evaluative, associative, as well as all information accompanying the anthroponym, which in the speech act carries information about the speech situation, the status of the interlocutors, about the assessment of the named, etc.) content. The cumulative function inherent in language determines the possibility of accumulating and reflecting nationalcultural pragmatic information in anthroponyms. It is this aspect of anthropolexics, which has been studied much less than others, and is analyzed in detail in this work. Thus, the relevance of the dissertation is determined by the widespread prevalence of anthroponyms in various spheres of language use and the need to study them as a linguistic sign, for the semiotic nature of a proper name is understood ambiguously. The problems associated with the study of anthroponyms from the standpoint of their communicative nature, including from the point of view of their pragmatic functions, have not been sufficiently developed. In numerous works on onomastics, far from all the problems of a proper name are covered, in particular, there is no consistent description of pragmatic situations of generating additional information in the process of stylistic functioning of a proper name in a literary text. The scientific novelty of the proposed work is determined by

the linguopragmatic perspective of considering a proper name included in communication, which implies an analysis of the peculiarities of its psycholinguistic properties, and “psycholinguistic research of a proper name has not yet been carried out on a large scale”

CONCLUSION. The scientific and practical significance of this work lies in the fact that its provisions and conclusions can be applied in the practice of linguoculturological studies of the national and cultural specifics of anthroponymic vocabulary in modern languages. The research results can be used in university courses "Introduction to Linguistics", "General Linguistics", "Lexicology", "Country Studies", as well as in special courses on onomastics, stylistics and semasiology. The dissertation materials can be useful in compiling linguistic and culturally oriented manuals, since, for example, “English proper names, despite all their specificity and importance for foreign language learners, are given negligible attention both in practical and theoretical courses of the English language”. The data of the dissertation research can be used to create Russian and English dictionaries of pragmatically meaningful anthroponyms.

References:

1. Кубрякова Е. С. Язык и знание. – М.: Языки славянской культуры, 2004. – 560 с.
2. Егорова Т. П. Семиотическая функция имени // Ономастика. Материалы к серии Народы мира и культура. – Вып. XXV.- Ч. I. – М.: РАН, 1993. – С. 21-28.
3. Nig'monov, A., Rustamiy, S., Nasirova, M., & Djafarov, B. (2020). Lexical Parallels Used In The Quatrains In The Dīwān Lughāt Al-Turk. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(3), 5301-5305.
4. Slobodian, A. S., & Norets, M. V. (2019). To The Problem Of Translation Into English Of Crimean Toponyms And Anthroponyms. *Modern Science*, (3), 323-326.
5. Давлатова, Р. Ҳ. (2020). Studies functional-semantic field of deixis in the Uzbek language. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(3), 404-409.
6. Sharei, S., Yazdanmehr, E., & Firoozian Pour Esfahani, A. (2017). Translation of anthroponyms in children’s cartoons: A comparative analysis of English dialogues and Persian subtitles. *Journal of Language and Translation*, 7(4), 21-31.
7. Лутфуллаева, Д., Давлатова, Р., & Тожибоев, Б. (2019). Ассоциативный словарь узбекского языка. Ташкент: «NAVOIY UNIVERSITETI».
7. Sabirova, M., & Saparniyazova, M. (2021). Naming Of Newspaper Text: Pragmatic Properties Of The Title. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(02), 18-22.
8. Rustamiy, S. (2018). Typological peculiarities of science of balaghah, rhetoric and stylistics. *The Light of Islam*, 2018(1), 16.
9. Juraev, Z. M., & Masalieva, O. M. (2020). Eleven Ahmad Pilgrimage And Seal And Flag Of Victory. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(12), 43-50.
10. МАСАЛИЕВА, О. М. (2021). ТАЗКИРАЛАРТАРИХИЙ МУҲИМ МАНБА СИФАТИДА. In *Uzbek Conference Publishing Hub* (Vol. 1, No. 01, pp. 123-130).
11. Judickaitė-Pašvenskienė, L. (2013). Translation of Anthroponyms in Children's Cartoons: a comparative analysis of English dialogue and Lithuanian subtitles. *New Voices in Translation Studies*, (10).